

Collaborative Development Framework For Electric Software-Defined Vehicles

The key objectives of the project encompass the development of digital design tools and a reliable methodology for electric SDVs. It aims to enhance the efficiency and reliability of sharing SDV architecture components while also speeding up development processes.

CODE4EV focuses on establishing five assets through three different Use Cases during the project duration:

- Collaborative Development Framework
- Tailored Electric SDV Architecture
- Optimal Powertrain Design & Control
- EV Health Monitoring & Predictive Maintenance
- Smart motion control

The project started on January 01, 2025 with a project duration of 36 months and is coordinated by TU Ilmenau, Germany. The total costs of the project amount to € 4.995.981.25.

CODE4EV is selected under the "Towards zero emission road transport" partnership (2Zero).

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

As we move toward a more connected and electrified future, software-defined vehicles (SDVs) are set to play a crucial role in shaping the automotive landscape.

CODE4EV is dedicated to advancing the field of software-defined vehicles (SDVs) by establishing a collaborative framework to support the design, production and operational phases of electric vehicles.

This ambitious initiative brings together 14 distinguished partners from eight European countries, each contributing their unique expertise and innovative spirit to address critical challenges facing our communities.

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